

Research Projects By Gulak

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Heartbeat & Body Temperature Monitoring System

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DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF HEARTBEAT AND BODY TEMPERATURE MONITORING SYSTEM

Dedication

I dedicate this project to Almighty God, the Creator, Cherisher, Nourisher, and Sustainer, who granted me the strength, ability, and life throughout the construction and implementation of this project. It is by His grace that I stand here today.

This project report is also dedicated to my entire family, Mohammed and Hauwa Muhammad, for their unwavering support, both financially and physically, during the entire period of implementing this project. Your encouragement and belief in me kept me going.

I extend my dedication to my project supervisor, Engr. Silas Edwin Nduku, for his invaluable guidance and supervision during this project. To my dear brothers, sister, and other relatives, including Abdullahi Sahuda, Caleb Samaila Kemuel, and many others, I offer my heartfelt thanks for your unending support and valuable advice throughout the construction of this device.

I also dedicate this report to those relatives I haven't mentioned, who contributed in various ways and prayed for the successful completion of this project. Your support did not go unnoticed, and I am deeply grateful.

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Abstract

The Heartbeat and Temperature Monitoring System presented in this project represents a novel approach to healthcare technology, designed to provide real-time monitoring of vital signs for enhanced health management. This system combines state-of-the-art sensors, microcontroller technology, and user-friendly interfaces to offer a comprehensive solution for tracking and analyzing heart rate and body temperature. The project utilizes an Arduino ATmega328P microcontroller, a Pulse Sensor for heart rate monitoring, and a DS18B20 temperature sensor for accurate temperature measurement. The data collected is displayed on an LCD 16x2 screen for user convenience and can be transmitted to a mobile application via Bluetooth for remote monitoring and analysis. The system underwent rigorous testing, including subsystem tests for the sensor, microcontroller, and display units, as well as functionality tests to ensure compliance with predefined requirements. Results from both simulation and real-world testing demonstrated the system's accuracy and reliability in monitoring vital signs. The Heartbeat and Temperature Monitoring System holds the potential to make a significant impact in healthcare by empowering individuals to take charge of their health and enabling healthcare providers to access valuable data for diagnosis and treatment. This project serves as a testament to the possibilities that arise when technology and healthcare intersect, offering a glimpse into the future of personalized health management.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Science and technology by way of inventions and innovations has made life easier for everybody in all spheres of life. One of such is in medical sciences where medical personnel are now able to acquire vital medical data from patients. Two of the most important are the measurement of heartbeat rate and temperature. The Human Heart Rate Monitors (HRM) are devices that allow the user to gain a real time measurement of their heart beat. They consist of a transmitter which detects the heartbeat by measuring the number of times the heart beats per minute and a receiver that determines the heart rate on receiving signals from the transmitter. Human Cardiovascular System consists of the heart, blood vessels and approximately five liters of blood that the blood vessels transport. Heart rate measurement indicates the soundness of the human cardiovascular system. Heartbeat rate is one of the very important parameters of the cardiovascular system. The measurement of heart rate is used by medical professionals to assist in the diagnosis and tracking of medical conditions. It is also used by individuals, such as athletes, who are interested in monitoring their heart rate to acquire maximum efficiency.

Variations in BT measurements can be dependent on the measurement site and method. The chosen site and method also influence convenience and reliability of measurements (Wettstein, 2018). It can be distinguished between invasive and non-invasive measurement methods. Non-invasive methods include oral, axillia, tympanic membrane and body surface measurements. Invasive methods include rectal (gold standard), esophagus, and pulmonary artery and urinary bladder measurements. Measurements of thermometers are thereby based on thermistors, thermocouple sensors or infrared waves. Exposure to high or low environmental temperatures can have an influence on BT and lead to hyper- or hypothermia. Both cause untreated disabilities and can lead to death. Hypothermia is the event where the BT drops below the normal range. Other reasons for hypothermia include infections and bacteremia, ethanol or drug ingestion, a central nervous system event, cachexia from malignancy or malnutrition, gastrointestinal bleeding and endocrine deficiencies. A BT exceeding the normal range can be hyperthermia or a fever. Hypothermia, sometimes as well called heat stroke, is induced by the body's inability to lose enough heat in comparison to an uncontrolled heat production. It can be a common occurrence during prolonged stays in very hot and humid regions. Other possible reasons for hyperthermia include neuroleptic malignant syndrome, serotonin syndrome, endocrinopathy, cerebral hemorrhage, hypothalamic injury and drug-induced hyperthermia. Hyperthermia should not be confused with fever, which is a controlled increase of BT induced by the hypothalamus thermoregulation. Reasons for fever include viral and bacterial infections, microbial toxins, and

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mediators of inflammation or immune reactions. Heart rate (HR) measures the number of contractions of the heart as beats per minute (bpm) and is regulated by the synchronous cooperation of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system. A healthy person has a resting HR between 60 and 100 bpm. Athletic people tend to have a lower resting HR than 60 bpm, dropping sometimes as low as 40 bpm. HR is adjusted depending on the physical activity and therefore on the body's need of oxygen and the removal of carbon dioxide. Various factors can change the HR based on the resting frequency the most important ones are according to the American Health Association (Wettstein, 2018).

1.2 Statement of Problem

As a result of the lifestyle and unhealthy eating habits there is a dramatic increase in incidents of heart and vascular diseases. Consequently, heart problems are on the increase on younger patients. Statistics shows that coronary heart disease is now the leading cause of death. Thus, any improvements in the diagnosis and treatment tools are welcomed by the medical community. In a clinical environment, heart rate is measured under controlled conditions like blood measurement, heart beat measurement, listening to heartbeats using Stethoscope and Electrocardiogram (ECG), but these methods are expensive and need to be carryout by an experience medical personnel. Therefore, there is a great need that patients are able to measure the heart rate in the home environment as well. Heatstroke condition are caused by your body overheating, usually as a result of prolonged exposure to or physical exertion in high temperatures. This most serious form of heat injury, heatstroke, can occur if your body temperature rises to 104 F (40C) or higher. The condition is most common in the summer months. Heatstroke requires emergency treatment. Untreated heatstroke can quickly damage your brain, heart, kidneys and muscles. The damage worsens the longer treatment is delayed, increasing your risk of serious complications or death. Heat stroke symptoms are high body temperature, altered mental state or behavior. Confusion, agitation, slurred speech, irritability, delirium, seizures and coma can all result from heatstroke. Alteration in sweating. In heatstroke brought on by hot weather, skin will feel hot and dry to the touch. However, in heatstroke brought on by strenuous exercise, skin may feel dry or slightly moist. Nausea and vomiting also one of the symptoms (Sharief, 2011).

In today's era, health problems are increasing day-by day at a high pace. The death rate of 55.3 million people dying each year or 151,600 people dying each day or 6316 people dying each hour is a big issue for all over the world. Hence it is the need of hour to overcome such problems. We, therefore, proposing a change in wireless sensors technology by designing a system which included different wireless sensors to receive information with respective human body temperature, blood pressure, saline level, heart rate etc. that will be undoubtedly further transmitted on an IoT platform which is accessible by the user via

internet. An accessible database is created about patient's health history which can be further monitored & analyzed by the doctor if necessary. The data storage can be saved on the server permanently or can be reset via the software. This paper proposes a health monitoring system which is capable of detecting multiple parameters of our body such as temperature, heart rate. Also, in case of emergency, automatically generating alerts will be sent to doctors and family members if any unusual activity is detected by or near the patient.

Over the last 20 years, heart rate monitors (HRMs) have become a widely used training aid for a variety of sports. The development of new HRMs has also evolved rapidly during the last two decades. In addition to heart rate (HR) responses to exercise, research has recently focused more on heart rate variability (HRV). Increased HRV has been associated with lower mortality rate and is affected by both age and sex. During graded exercise, the majority of studies show that HRV decreases progressively up to moderate intensities, after which it stabilizes. There is abundant evidence from cross-sectional studies that trained individuals have higher HRV than untrained individuals. The results from longitudinal studies are equivocal, with some showing increased HRV after training but an equal number of studies showing no differences. The duration of the training programmes might be one of the factors responsible for the versatility of the results. HRMs are mainly used to determine the exercise intensity of a training session or race as its Compared with other indications of exercise intensity, HR is easy to monitor, is relatively cheap and can be used in most situations. In addition, HR and HRV could potentially play a role in the prevention and detection of overtraining. The effects of overreaching on submaximal HR are controversial, with some studies showing decreased rates and others no difference. Maximal HR appears to be decreased in almost all 'overreaching' studies (Prakash, 2018)

There appears to be a small day-to-day variability in HR and a steady increase during exercise has been observed in most studies. Furthermore, factors such as dehydration and ambient temperature can have a profound effect on the HR-VO (2) relationship. (Achten and Jeukendrup 2003).

Recent advancement in wearable technologies, particularly smart watches embedded with powerful processors, memory subsystems with various built-in sensors such as accelerometer, gyroscope and optical sensor in one single package has opened a whole new application space. One of the main applications of interest is the monitoring of movement patterns, heart rate, ECG and PPG particularly for longer durations in natural environments. The heart rate acquired from the smartwatch is reasonably accurate with a high degree of correlation. (Phan et al. 2015)

1.3 Aim and Objective of Study

The aim of this project is to design heartbeat and body temperature monitoring system

1. The basic objective of this project, is to integrate and interface heartbeat and body temperature sensors with a microcontroller.
2. To design and implement a software program that will enable the sensors to ensure accurate and reliable measurements.
3. To construct a fully functional prototype of the monitoring system that meets the defined specifications and standards, ensuring its effectiveness in measuring.

1.4 Significance of the Study

(Prakash, 2018) In recent years, physiological monitoring has benefited significantly from developments in the field of flexible circuits and the integration of sensing technology into wearable items (Barbaro et al. 2010). An ear-worn, flexible, low-power PPG sensor for heart rate monitoring was introduced by Patterson et al., that the sensor is suited for long-term monitoring due to its location and unobtrusive design. Although systems of this type have shown promising results, additional work appears to be necessary to achieve motion artifact reduction (Yan and Zhang 2008) (Wood and Asada 2007). Proper attenuation of motion artifacts is essential to the deployment of wearable sensors. Some of the problems due to motion artifacts could be minimized by integrating sensors into tight fitting garments. A comparative analysis of different wearable systems for monitoring respiratory function was presented by. (Lanata et al. 2010).

The analysis showed that piezoelectric pneumography performs better than spirometry. Nonetheless, further advances in signal processing techniques to mitigate motion artifacts are needed. Biochemical sensors have recently gained a great deal of interest among researchers in the field of wearable technology. These types of sensors can be used to monitor the bio-chemistry as well as levels of chemical compounds in the atmosphere (e.g. to facilitate monitoring people working in hazardous environments). From a design point of view, biochemical sensors are perhaps the most complex as they often require collection, analysis and disposal of body fluids. Advances in the field of wearable biochemical sensors has been slow, but research has recently picked up pace due to the development of micro and nano fabrication technologies (Dudde et al. 2006) developed a minimally-invasive wearable closed-loop quasi-continuous drug infusion system that measures blood glucose levels and infuses insulin automatically. The glucose monitor consists of a novel silicon sensor that continuously measures glucose levels using a micro perfusion technique and continuous infusion of insulin is achieved by a modified advanced insulin pump. The device has integrated Bluetooth communication capability for displaying and logging data and receiving commands from a personal digital assistant (PDA) device (Patel et al. 2012).

1.5 Scope of the Study

The scope of this project aimed at utilizing XD-58C pulse sensor module for heartbeat measurement, a DS18B20 module sensor for body temperature measurement, Arduino Uno R3 and a 16x2 LCD display for real-time data visualization of which these components are interfaced with the Atmega328P microcontroller, with firmware and software development conducted in C++. The software incorporate algorithms for capturing and processing heartbeat and temperature data, enabling real-time display and user interaction on the LCD screen. The project encompass hardware integration, thorough testing and validation which aims to deliver a reliable and user-friendly monitoring system for healthcare applications, combining accuracy and ease of use.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERITURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter constitute related research works based on heart rate and body temperature monitoring system (HRMBTS) which refer to a simple device that takes a sample of the heartbeat signal and computes the heart rate in beats per minutes (bpm) so that the information can easily be used to track heart conditions. This chapter emphasis electrical and optical methods as means of detecting and acquiring heart signals. Because ECG and blood pressure monitor are amongst a few medical devices that display heartbeat readings digitally.

2.2 Concept of Problem

2.2.1 Human Heart

The heart is a muscular organ in humans and other animals which pumps blood through the blood vessels of the circulatory system. Blood provides the body with oxygen and nutrients, and also assists in the removal of metabolic wastes. It is located in the middle compartment of the mediastinum in the chest and it performs its functions with repeated heartbeats. A heartbeat refers to a two-part pumping action of the heart that takes about a second. These are the diastole and the systole (Hendryani et al., 2021).

2.2.1.1 The Diastole

As blood collects in the upper chambers (the left and right atria), the heart's natural pacemaker (the SA node) sends out an electrical signal that causes the atrium to contract. This contraction pushes blood through the tricuspid and mitral valves into the resting lower chambers (right and left ventricles). This part of the two-part pumping phase (the longer of the two) is called the diastole (Hendryani et al., 2021).

2.2.1.2 The Systole

This is the second part of the pumping phase which occurs when the ventricles are full of blood. The electrical signals from the SA node travel along a pathway of cells to the ventricles causing them to contract. This is called the systole. As the tricuspid and mitral valves shut tight to prevent a backflow of blood, other valves open thus blood is pushed from the right ventricle to the lungs first to pick up oxygen before it is transmitted to the heart and other parts of the body (Hendryani et al., 2021).

2.2.2 Heartbeat Rate

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The rate at which the heart beats is not constant. A heartbeat rate refers to the number of heartbeats per unit time, usually expressed in beats per minute (BPM). The heartbeat rate can vary according to the demands of the muscles to absorb oxygen and excrete carbon dioxide, thus, it changes during sleep and exercises. It also varies significantly between individuals based on age, fitness and genetics (George, 2013).

2.3 Electrical System of the Heart

Figure 1 Electrical system of the heart

The heart's muscle is made of tiny cells and the electrical system of the heart controls the timing of the heartbeat by sending an electrical signal through these cells. Two different types of cell in the heart enable the electrical signal to control the heartbeat. These are:

- a) Conducting cells which carry the heart's electrical signals.
- b) Muscle cells which enable the heart's chambers to contract, an action triggered by the heart's electrical signal.

This electrical signal travels through the network of conducting cell pathways which stimulate the upper and lower chambers to contract. The signal is able to travel along these pathways by means of a complex reaction that allows each cell to activate the one next to it, stimulating it to "pass along" the signal in an orderly manner. As each cell rapidly transmits this electrical charge, the entire heart contracts in one coordinated motion, creating a heartbeat.

The electrical system starts in a group of cells at the top of the heart called the “Sino-Atrial (SA) Node”. The signal then travels down the heart, triggering first the two atria and ventricles. In a healthy heart, the signals travel very quickly through the heart, allowing the chambers to contract in a smooth orderly fashion.

The heart’s electrical system controls the timing of the heartbeat by regulating:

- a) The heart rate (in BPM), and
- b) The heart rhythm i.e. the synchronised pumping action of the four heart chambers.

The heart’s electrical system during normal functioning should maintain a heart rate of 60 to 100 beats per minute when a person is at rest. It increases this rate to meet the needs of the body during physical activities and lowers it during sleep. It also maintains an orderly contraction of the atria and ventricles. This is called “Sinus Rhythm” (George, 2013).

2.4 Heat stroke

Heat stroke is a medical emergency symbolize by a high body temperature, altered mental status and, in classical heat stroke ,hot , dry flushes skin (hristopher, 2016). heat stroke could start to multi-organ damage with haemorrhage and necrosis in the lungs, heart ,liver, kidney, brain and gut (hristopher, 2016). heat stoke occurs when the core body temperature hike against a falling thermoregulatory system (hristopher, 2016).

Cardiovascular Diseases

Diseases generally refers to conditions that involve narrowed or blocked vessels that can lead to a heart attack,chest pain(angina) or stroke (hristopher, 2016).

2.4.1 Effects of heat stroke

The result of these effects is that the body surface temperature rises. When this situation continues for a long time, the dehydration caused by sweating progresses and, when combined with blood being retained at the dilated peripheral blood vessels, blood volume (Rubasri et.al. 2015). The result of these effects is that the body surface temperature rises. When this situation continues for a long time, the dehydration caused by sweating progresses and, when combined with blood being retained at the dilated peripheral blood vessels, blood volume decreases (Rubasri et.al. 2015).

2.4.2Effect of cardiovascular Diseases

The term "heart disease" is often used interchangeably with the term "cardiovascular disease."

Cardiovascular disease generally refers to conditions that involve narrowed or blocked blood vessels that

can lead to a heart attack, chest pain (angina) or stroke. Other heart conditions, such as those that affect your heart's muscle, valves or rhythm, also are considered forms of heart disease. Many forms of heart disease can be prevented or treated with healthy lifestyle cardiovascular disease symptoms may be different for men and women. For instance, men are more likely to have chest pain; women are more likely to have other symptoms along with chest discomfort, such as shortness of breath, nausea and extreme fatigue. Symptoms can include: • Chest pain, chest tightness, chest pressure and chest discomfort (angina) • Shortness of breath • Pain, numbness, weakness or coldness in your legs or arms if the blood vessels in those parts of your body are narrowed • Pain in the neck, jaw, throat, upper abdomen or back choices (Rubasri et.al. 2015).

Overheated >180 breaths / min	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Dramatic rise in body temperature• High gut permeability• Increased passage of endotoxins & pathogens	Death 34°C	Air temperature
Hot 50-180 breaths / min	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Spread out• Lower feed intake• Increased floor contact• Increased body temperature• Increased splashing, fouling	30°C 27°C	
Comfortable 20-30 breaths / min	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Normal behavior	23°C 18°C	

Figure 2 Effect of Cardiovascular Disease

2.4.3 Factors of heat stroke

Risk factors may be present but are not requisite. The onset of heat stroke is rapid, and patients may have a prodrome of weakness, headache, chills, ataxia, and nausea. Chest pain may be present, as well as shortness of breath and abdominal pain. Thirst is not a reliable indicator of impending heat stroke. The body temperature rises rapidly, sweating ceases, and multiple system failure ensues (usually heralded by neurological problems). An acute phase inflammatory reaction appears to be involved in the progression from heat exhaustion to heat stroke. During heat stroke fever is 104°F (40°C) or greater. Sweating usually ceases and the skin becomes hot and dry (Pawan, 2018). Confusion, delirium, and ataxia are followed by loss of consciousness. Some patients will have seizures that usually occur during cooling. Tachycardia and hyperventilation are common vital sign changes. Laboratory examination reveals an elevated hematocrit (secondary to hemoconcentration), electrolyte and acid-base disturbances (typically hyponatremia,

metabolic acidosis, and hypokalemia), and evidence of muscle, renal, and hepatic damage. The electrocardiogram and cardiac enzymes may indicate myocardial injury. Thrombocytopenia can be profound if disseminated intravascular coagulation has occurred (Pawan, 2018)

Factors of Cardiovascular

Development of atherosclerosis While cardiovascular disease can refer to different heart or blood vessel problems, the term is often used to mean damage to your heart or blood vessels by atherosclerosis (ath-ur-o-skluh-ROE-sis), a buildup of fatty plaques in your arteries. Plaque buildup thickens and stiffens artery walls, which can inhibit blood flow through your arteries to your organs and tissues. Atherosclerosis is also the most common cause of cardiovascular disease. It can be caused by correctable problems, such as an unhealthy diet, lack of exercise, being overweight and smoking.

Figure 3 Development of atherosclerosis in Today's liveLifesapanFitness.com

2.5 Heart rate Monitoring Systems

Generally, the patient monitoring system is one of the major advancements in the global health care program due to its improved technology. It is capable of measuring various body conditions of a patient like the temperature, heartbeat rate or the level of oxygen in the blood, using embedded technology. This advancement in technology was necessitated by the increased occurrence of cardio-vascular diseases which usually occur as a result of abnormalities in the heart condition of an individual (WHO, 2007). Obviously,

it is difficult to keep track of the abnormalities in the heart by manual means, hence the need for heartbeat counters.

It is synonymous with a heart rate monitor hence these two terms will be used interchangeably throughout this project. Since the heart is one of the most important organs in the human body, it is imperative that these devices are designed with a very high degree of accuracy. Apart from construction defects and sensor technologies, the accuracy of the heartbeat counter depends on the part of the human body from which it is measured. The three most popular areas are the chest, the fingertip and the wrist.

2.5.1 The Chest

This is the most accurate means of heart rate monitoring as it remains very close to the heart. This type of monitor is strapped to the chest region with the help of appropriate support and it is linked to a display unit which displays the rate of the heartbeat. The display unit can be a simple monitor placed on a wristwatch, which signals by giving a beep sound when the heart rate crosses a certain limit.

2.5.2 The Fingertips

These may also be called pulse-type monitors and they measure the heartbeat rate when the finger is placed on it. This technology employs the use of optical sensors to measure the alteration in blood volume at the fingertips, with each heartbeat. This little alteration can be converted to a pulse, which is counted to determine the heart rate.

2.5.3 The wrists

These monitors operate on the same basic principle as the pulse-type monitors but their circuits are usually built into a wristband for the comfort of the user. Some wrist-based monitors utilise the pressure felt on the wrists with each heartbeat, to determine the heart rate. It is the least accurate type of monitor because by the time the blood reaches the capillaries in the wrists, it could have slowed down significantly. Most of them also require the user to remain absolutely still, while taking measurements.

2.6 Heart Rate Monitors

Physiologic monitors have been in regular commercial production since 1954. In recognition of the past 62 years, various heart rate monitoring devices have been invented with different degrees of accuracy and technological applications (Himmelstein, 1950). Before we review various constructions done on this project topic in recent times, it is imperative we look at the evolution of these monitoring devices over the years and the various improvements that have been made, to make them what they are today.

2.6.1 Brief History of Heart Rate Monitors

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The first heart rate monitor came into existence in the 1950's and was then called the "Cardiotachoscope". It featured the Cathode Ray Tube (CRT) to view the Electrocardiogram (ECG) i.e. the electrical activities of the heart, a heart rate indicator, alarm systems for high and low heart rates and a connection to a conventional electrocardiograph for printouts (Himmelstein, 1950). It was only during this era that its name was ever used and it was never even found to enter into production, thus, its exclusion from many historical documents.

2.6.1.1 The 1950's: Early Warning Systems for Cardiac Accidents

Monitors of this era were often referred to as electrocardioscopes or cardioscopes. Sometimes they were simply referred to as an oscilloscope. Unlike modern monitors, devices of this era had monochrome displays and the persistence of the wave was generally not sufficient to cover the screen. This meant that the ECG waveform would show only a second or two of new data. The old data would fade away and the trace has been described as a bouncing ball with a comets tail. Some CRT's were of the "long persistence" type which meant that fading was slower and more waveform was visible. There were no numeric parameters or annotations on the screen (Dornette, 1964). The advantage of the monitor was the immediacy of the information and the ability to generate alarms. Most devices had an output connector to allow direct printing on a standard electrocardiograph. Controls on these monitors generally allowed for lead selection, focus adjustment, intensity or brightness control, sensitivity or gain control, vertical trace-position control, and sweep rate adjustment.

However, a challenge with monitors of this era was the presentation of heart rate information. Many early units did not provide a cardio-tachometer or rate-meter to provide a heart rate. Also, most bedside type monitors often had round screens of about 5 inches in diameter. Some had only 3 inch diameter screens and so, monitors were limited to one or two waveform traces (Cardiol, 1972).

2.6.1.2 The 1970's: The Impact of Digital Electronics

The decade of the 1970's saw some significant improvements in the presentation of the displayed waveforms and information. This was a result of the incorporation of digital electronics and, eventually, microprocessors. Real time (centrally controlled and processed) arrhythmia analysis appeared at the beginning of the decade and evolved over the duration of the 1970's. Standards documents which established minimum performance criteria for physiologic monitors began appearing from several bodies such as the "Specification for Biomedical Monitoring Systems" X-1414 of 1970 from the Veterans Administration (Cromwell, 1976)

The appearance of the so called “Memory Monitor” occurred at the beginning of the decade. These monitors incorporated analog to digital converters and small memories to briefly store several seconds of incoming data. The stored data was then used to define the display on the CRT. The advantage of this scheme was that the stored data could be written to the screen quickly and repeatedly at the same location well before it would fade out resulting in a “non-fade” persistent display. Waveform data was presented either as a moving wave that scrolls from right to left or as a stationary waveform that is overwritten by the trailing left edge of a narrow "eraser bar" which travels from left to right. Modern monitors use one display method or they permit selection of either of these modes of display. Some memory monitors also allowed data to be cascaded (Glaeser, 1975). This meant that an ECG trace would continue on the line below thereby providing more visible information over a greater time period. The display of most memory monitors could also be stopped or “frozen” for review of the appearance of a particular waveform. Also, printing or viewing of several seconds preceding an alarm condition was possible with some systems.

The middle of the decade saw the introduction of microprocessors and thus the beginning of modern monitoring systems. Spacelab claims to have launched the first (bedside) monitoring system which incorporated microprocessor technology in 1974. Among other things, microprocessors enabled further exploitation of the CRT as a means to display information. By 1978 some vendors such as Hewlett Packard and Philips began integrating the heart rate information on the CRT display as a numeric value (in models HP78341A and HP78342A and Philips model CM-120). In summary, heart rate presentation evolved over the course of the decade from a bar-graph display to a numeric LED display located next to the CRT on the front panel and then to a numeric integrated with the CRTs’ display (Biloon, 1978).

2.6.1.3 Timeline of Other Previous Works:

Summarily, the evolution of the monitors is as shown

1950: First ‘modern’ monitor reported in use.

1954: First appearance of production monitors (Cambridge cardioscope).

1956: Production monitors enter clinical use (Electrodyne PM-65).

1966: Non-circular displays and Nixie numeric indicators are employed.

1968: Heart rate included on CRT as a progress-bar indicator.

1970: The memory monitor appears which allows for a non-fade display. Isolated inputs appear for added patient safety.

1975: LEDs employed as numeric indicators on physiologic monitors.

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1978: Monitor displays include heart rate as a numeric on the CRT.

1980: Modern modular parameter modules appear.

1983: Arrhythmia analysis available at the bedside. The first color physiologic monitors appear.

1990: Transport monitors appear which could transfer the same patients' module and cabling to a compatible bedside monitor. Flatscreen (non-CRT) monitors appear on physiologic monitors.

1995: Some monitors can run Windows applications.

1996: Continuum of care monitors appears and parameter modules begin to be replaced by configured acquisition panels on the side of monitors.

2000: Internet connectivity at the bedside becomes available.

2005: Wireless monitoring systems gain popularity, reducing cable clutter and allowing for increased mobility of patients. 2008: Touchscreen displays become common in patient monitors, improving user interface and ease of use. 2010: Integration of electronic health record (EHR) systems with patient monitors for seamless data transfer and storage. 2012: Remote monitoring capabilities expand, enabling healthcare professionals to access patient data remotely via secure networks. 2015: Advanced data analytics and machine learning algorithms are integrated into patient monitors, enabling predictive monitoring and early detection of anomalies. 2017: Portable and wearable patient monitors gain traction, allowing patients to monitor their health outside of clinical settings. 2020: The COVID-19 pandemic accelerates the development of telehealth solutions, leading to increased demand for remote patient monitoring. 2021: Patient monitors continue to evolve with improved connectivity, data security, and user-friendly interfaces, enhancing the quality of patient care.

This timeline illustrates the continuous advancement and innovation in patient monitoring technology, reflecting the growing importance of real-time data collection and analysis in modern healthcare

2.7 Previous Work Done

Among various methods employed in the construction of heartbeat counters is a simple, reliable, microcontroller-based device which demonstrates a technique to measure the alteration in blood volume at fingertip with each heartbeat. The sensor unit consists of an infrared light-emitting-diode (IR LED) and a photodiode, placed side by side as shown below. The IR diode transmits an infrared light into the fingertip (placed over the sensor unit), and the photodiode senses the portion of the light that is reflected back. The intensity of reflected light depends upon the blood volume inside the fingertip. So, each heart beat slightly

alters the amount of reflected infrared light that can be detected by the photodiode. With a proper signal conditioning, this little change in the amplitude of the reflected light can be converted into a pulse. The pulses can be later counted by the microcontroller to determine the heart rate which is displayed on a 3-digit, CA (Common Anode) display. See fig. 2.1 below

Figure 4 Heart Rate Measuring Device using PIC16F628A (Taken from Circuitstoday.com)

Once the start button is pressed, the microcontroller activates the IR transmission in the sensor unit for 15secs. During this interval, the numbers of pulses are counted and the number of heartbeats would be calculated by the microcontroller to be four (4) times the counted value (Hashem, 2010).

This device is not free from errors and several modifications can be made to improve its accuracy, sophistication and convenience. The work described above does not implement any form of alarm system either by use of a speaker, light indicator, e.t.c. to indicate and alert the user when the heartbeat count rises or falls off a certain threshold. Also, the alteration in the blood volume is too little to be measured directly by a microcontroller as is done above. It is therefore necessary to use a high gain amplifier to increase the signal significantly before it is applied to the microcontroller. All these modifications have been implemented in this project.

For the sake of convenience and mobility, many heart rate monitoring devices were incorporated into wristbands and wristwatches but heart rate measurement through the wrist, by transmission and reflection of light rays, and the consequent measurement of blood volume changes, comes at an unnecessary price.

One principal and mitigating issue to wrist-based monitors is skin-pigmentation (skin color) because the light has to penetrate through several layers of the skin. The higher the position of the person on the Fitzpatrick scale (a measure of skin tone), the greater the difficulty associated with the reflection of light (Bharat, 2008). Therefore, "...the heart rate monitor will not work if the user is very dark in complexion," (YaBoyMartell, 2011). From research carried out, it has been shown that light will reflect more easily on a smooth brighter skin than on a dark thick scruffy skin. The heartbeat counter will therefore give different readings for the same patient, when the heartbeat is counted from the wrist and from the fingertips. The palm of the hands is one of the lightest parts of the human body in terms of complexion; hence its result will be much more accurate than that of the wrist. Also, unlike the narrow, slow-pumping capillaries in the wrists, there is an arterial vessel at the tip of the forefinger which keeps up with even the fastest pulsations of the heart. Thanks to the translucency of the fingertip's skin, the heart rate is easy to read. It was therefore decided that measurement through the fingertip is the best and cheapest technique for a heartbeat count.

In terms of sensitivity, a very reliable heart rate monitor was proposed few years ago. Instead of the principle of photoplethysmography (measurement of blood volume through the use of light), pressure-sensing was introduced. Unlike other conventional methods, a flexible pressure sensor was designed with the capability of measuring the heart rate, by sensing the pulsations of the arteries in the wrists (YiShu, 2015). This design also incorporated an ASP (Analog Signal Processor) to extract the required signal in the midst of several noise input. It also had a counter, an indicator and a timing circuit to stop the measurement.

Despite the linearity of the pressure sensor, it was also not a perfect design, and it's extremely high sensitivity played a major role in sending it down the food chain. Noise could be easily introduced into the system by the muscle movements of the user. Also, its sensitivity needed improvement to distinguish between an actual pulse, and any other pressure associated with the arm; "...all movements occur as a result of a force, and every force is capable of causing pressure" (Anyakoha, 2007). It was even discovered that even dead patients (people without heartbeats) still recorded a pulse with this device. It was thus unanimously decided that this device was not suitable for use in hospitals and other very important applications.

Roughly two years ago, a heartbeat counter capable of maintaining the heart rate and making an alarm at heightened levels of the heart pulse was introduced. It was constructed using a 4026IC and had an in-built counter and seven-segment drivers embedded in a single IC. It also employed the use of two mono-stable multivibrators, one for enabling the counter for one minute, and the other for feeding pulses from the heartbeat sensor circuitry. With the aid of a buzzer, a sound is produced when the heart rate goes above

80BPM. The incorporated alarm, the cost and ease of construction were only part of its advantages (Jaseem, 2014). See the circuit shown in fig. 2.3.2

Figure 5 Heart rate monitor using 4026 IC (Culled from CircuitsGallery.com)

However, the count was represented by two 7-segment displays multiplexed together meaning the device could not give a reading above 99BPM. Besides that, each of the displays was associated with one of the 4026IC's and an extra IC would be required for an extra display. Generally speaking, there are a lot of advantages of using the LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) over the 7-segment LED (Light Emitting Diode) some of which includes a built-in processing power, character generators, fewer I/O lines required and the ability to easily represent complex/special characters. This is why a LCD was implemented in this project. Further details about this display will be discussed as we progress in this chapter.

Further research on various heart rate monitors showed many more methods of counting the heartbeat, one of which is achieved using the Pulse Oximeter (Lai, 2009). This device uses optical sensors and LEDs emit light at different wavelengths. The LED will emit light through the finger and then the transmitted light is detected using an optical sensor. The heart pulse can be obtained from the value of oxygen saturation level which can be obtained based on the principle of oxygenated haemoglobin which having a higher absorption coefficient for infrared light than deoxygenated haemoglobin, will observe more red light.

It was also discovered that the wireless pressure pulse system consists of a transmitter, a receiver, and a PC capable of recording online data. The device measured and displayed a pulse rate and the saturation of haemoglobin in the arterial blood. A LED was also used to emit light so that it is transmitted through an artery, and the resistance of the photo-resistor is determined by the amount of light reaching it. With each

contraction of the heart, blood is forced to extremities and the amount of blood in the finger increases which is why the finger is suitable for the measurement of the pulse rate (Laghrouche, 2010).

Based on all these reviews, various modifications were made and a simple, cheap, reliable circuit capable of accurately counting the heartbeat was derived with the use of a microcontroller, a sensor and other relevant components. These components are reviewed below.

2.8 Related Research Works

According to a research carried out by Prakash 2018 et., all, on a project entitled “heart rate monitoring system” makes mentioned that Heartbeat Sensor is an electronic device that is used to measure the heart rate i.e. speed of the heartbeat. Monitoring body temperature, heart rate and blood pressure are the basic things that to do in order to keep life healthy. In order to measure the body temperature, they use thermometers and a sphygmomanometer to monitor the Arterial Pressure or Blood Pressure. They says that Heart Rate can be monitored in two ways: one way is to manually check the pulse either at wrists or neck and the other way is to use a Heartbeat Sensor. Pulse oximetry is used in this project to detect the heartbeat using fingers. When the heart expands (diastole) the volume of blood inside the fingertip increases and when the heart contracts (systole) the volume of blood inside the fingertip decreases. The resultant pulsing of blood volume inside the fingertip is directly proportional to the heart rate and if you could somehow count the number of pulses in one minute, that’s the heart rate in beats per minute (bpm). For this an IR transmitter/receiver pair (LED) placed in close contact with the fingertip. When the heart beats, the volume of blood cells under the sensor increases and this reflects more IR waves to sensor and when there is no beat the intensity of the reflected beam decreases. The pulsating reflection is converted to a suitable current or voltage pulse by the sensor. The sensor output is processed by suitable electronic circuits to obtain a visible indication (digital display). Their result for the heart rate monitoring system was successfully made and worked fine. The Heartbeat Monitoring System is the part of Patient Monitoring System, can be extended to measure other parameters of patient like ECG & temperature etc. They conclude their project on the fact that Biomedical engineering (BME) is the application of engineering principles and techniques to the medical field. It combines the design and problem-solving skills of engineering with medical and biological sciences to improve patient’s health care and the quality of life of individuals.

Drawbacks with ECG method are: too many sensors and cables connections, fluctuations in the ECG signal baseline, power line noise, and interference due to muscular activities and high cost of procurement. More so, ECG is not suitable for continuous monitoring on burnt victims and the conduction gel used may cause discomfort and inflammation on the skin. The average heart beats is between 60 and 100 times per minute.

If your heart beats below 60 times per minute, this is bradycardia. If it beats more than 100 times per minute, is tachycardia. The rate of heartbeat is measured in beat per minute (bpm) (WebMD, 2011).

According to WebMD (2011) having bradycardia (pronounced as Bray-dee KAR-dee-uh) means that your heart beats slower than normal. For majority people, heart rate of between 60–100 beats per minute is considered normal while at rest. Heart beats less than 60 times a minute, is slower than normal. Slow heart rate can be normal and healthy or it could be a sign of problem with the heart's electrical system. For some people, slow heart rate does not cause any problem. It can be a sign of being very fit. Healthy young adults and athletics often have rates of less than 60 beats a minute. In other people, bradycardia is a sign of a problem with the heart. "It means that the heart's natural pacemaker is not working right or that the electrical pathways are disrupted". Men and women aged 65 and older are most likely to develop a slow heart rate that needs treatment. As a person ages, the electrical system of the heart often does not function normally, hence needs to be monitored frequently and regularly.

Chime, (2015) proposed a heart rate monitor using a low-cost microcontroller, AT89C52, from Atmel Corporation for his design. He measured heart rate from the fingertip using infra-led transmitter and receiver sensor box. The rate is then averaged and displayed on a text-based LCD, but does not have voice output to aid visually impaired persons which also also proposed a microcontroller-based heart rate monitor using fingertip sensors. The design uses the optical technology to detect the flow of blood through the fingertip. The microcontroller is programmed to acquire the signal, eliminate the zero-crossing problems of the digitized signal by Fourier transformation and display the heart rate on an LCD. A local audible alarm is also provided to indicate heart rate status. The device however requires expertise knowledge to use and also not so economical.

Hendryani (2021) et al., on a project called "Design and Development of LIVE Monitoring Heartbeat and Body Temperature Using the Internet of Things" they carried out that, Vital signs in the human body are statistical measures that determine health status, including heart rate per minute (BPM) and body temperature. Those two parameters correlate with a symptom of exposure to covid-19. Vital signs on patients with unstable health conditions should be checked regularly to determine preventive measures. Their study aimed to design a device to monitor heart rate and body temperature using the Internet of things technology. Their system can monitor the patient's heart rate and body temperature in real-time and record the vital sign's condition. Their project system uses a DSB1820 sensor, pulse sensor, and a Node MCVU3. The patient's heartbeat data and body temperature monitored using the LCD and web service with the Internet of things technology. The system test results show that the hardware system could monitor the data through web service. The system is useful as a health monitoring device for covid-19 patients without

symptoms the development of a heart rate measuring device using an IR base sensor and Arduino Uno has been carried out by Pawar et al. This device can measure heart rates from infants to adults.

The percentage of errors calculated from the readings and the maximum and minimum errors are 6.49% and 4.1%, respectively. Another development, namely the heart rate measurement, has been carried out by Kavsaoglu et al., 2014 by measuring the heart rate using the photoplethysmography method Bandana Mallick et al (2016). developed real time heart rate monitoring using fingertips and Arduino Uno. The results can monitor the heart rate then send it via Short Message Service (SMS). Stojanovic et al. made a headset to track covid-19 symptoms. They used a built-in microphone on mobile phones as a sensor to detect breathing problems, respiration rates, and cough. This device was simple but only limited to the symptoms mentioned before.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY, SYSTEM DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Introduction:

This chapter unveils the methodologies, design principles, and system analysis techniques that have contributed to its success, highlighting the dedication and innovation that have gone into making this groundbreaking system a reality where it is designed to provide a comprehensive foundation for comprehending the complex web of connections that bind heartbeat and body temperature. In this chapter, I embark on a journey that seeks to elucidate how heartbeat and body temperature are not isolated entities but rather interconnected components of our physiological orchestra. We delve into the mechanisms and regulatory systems that govern these vital signs, uncovering the subtle cues and signals they exchange.

Furthermore, this chapter illuminates the practical applications of understanding this symbiotic relationship. From personalized healthcare strategies to athletic performance optimization, we will delve into the diverse domains where this knowledge can be harnessed to improve human well-being.

Furthermore, the chapter explores how these systems have evolved over time, incorporating advancements in miniaturization, data analysis, and user interface design. We will consider the impact of such progress on the field of medicine and the potential future developments that hold promise for improving patient care.

The system design of the Heartbeat and Body Temperature monitoring system using Sensors is meant to detect abnormal pulses and temperature on a patient's body. The system methodology includes using a heartbeat or Ds18B20 signal detection to realize how patient's symptoms it is in order to attend the patient. The system repeatedly alerts the concerned persons until the patient recovers. This system has the advantages of high stability, wearable, low power consumption. This proposed method is designed using top to ground design implementation techniques. The two main parts of the system design is the detection module and the display unit. The detection module must be placed on the patient's hand while the display unit will always be with the specialist (doctor) or the patient's family members, so that whenever there is abnormality on the patient's temperature, they can easily be informed to control the situation. The detection module mainly includes physical signal detection sensor designed like a curve. The detection module consists of the patient's body sensor, an analog to digital converter (ADC), a clock pulse circuit within the atmega, and a regulated 9 volts battery power supply (PSU).

The first step in the system design procedure was the required information was gathered for the quoted system design specifications. The exact system components to be used were calculated and placed on a computer aided design software (Proteus 8) used for the design simulation of the project design. A

code written in C language program using Arduino IDE development Programme was used to actualize the design program.

3.2 Block Diagram

Figure 6 Block Diagram

SENSOR_UNIT

This unit comprises specialized sensors designed to capture and transmit crucial physiological information in real-time. Sensors within this unit detect the electrical signals generated by the heart's contractions, known as electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. These sensors are typically placed strategically on the body to ensure accurate readings. By continuously monitoring ECG signals, the sensor unit can track heart rate, rhythm, and detect abnormalities, enabling early intervention in cases of cardiac issues. The sensor unit also integrates temperature sensors, allowing for the simultaneous tracking of body temperature. These sensors provide a non-invasive and convenient method to monitor changes in body temperature, which can be indicative of infections, fever, or other health conditions.

Overall, the sensor unit in a heartbeat and body temperature monitoring system acts as the frontline data collector, facilitating the continuous and precise measurement of vital signs.

3.2.1 Heartbeat Sensor Module

A heartbeat sensor module, often referred to as a pulse sensor, is a device used to measure a person's heart rate or pulse rate. It is commonly used in various applications such as health monitoring devices, fitness trackers, and medical equipment. The sensor typically works by detecting the changes in blood volume within blood vessels as the heart beats.

3.2.1.1 A Pulse sensor

A pulse wave is the change in the volume of a blood vessel that occurs when the heart pumps blood, and a detector that monitors this volume change is called a pulse sensor.

Four main ways to measure heart rate:

Electrocardiogram, photoelectric pulse wave, blood pressure measurement and phonocardiography.

Pulse sensors use the photoelectric method as illustrated in figure below:

Figure 7 Photoelectric Method

Pulse sensors using the photoelectric pulse wave method are classified into 2 types depending on the measurement method: transmission and reflection.

- Transmission type's measure pulse waves by emitting red or infrared light from the body surface and detecting the change in blood flow during heart beats as a change in the amount of light transmitted through the body. This method is limited to areas where light can easily penetrate, such as the fingertip or earlobe.

ROHM is currently developing a reflection-type pulse sensor (Optical Sensor for Heart Rate Monitor).

Reflection-Type Pulse Sensor (Optical Sensor for Heart Rate Monitor)

- Reflection-type pulse sensors (Optical Sensors for Heart Rate Monitor) emit infrared, red, or green light (~550nm) towards the body and measure the amount of light reflected using a photodiode or phototransistor. Oxygenated hemoglobin present in the blood of the arteries has the characteristic

of absorbing incident light, so by sensing the blood flow rate (change in blood vessel volume) that changes following heart contractions over time we are able to measure the pulse wave signal.

3.2.1.2 Pulse Sensor Working Principle

The working principle of the pulse sensor is extremely simple. This sensor includes two faces where the first face is connected with an LED including an ambient light sensor whereas another face is connected with circuitry. This circuit aids in noise cancellation as well as amplification.

On the front side, the LED is connected to a vein as shown in Figure 3 of a human body (ear tips or Fingertip), however, it should be located directly on top of a vein. The LED produces light that will drop directly on the vein.

The veins in the body will have a flow of blood within them simply once the heart is pumping. So if we check the blood flow we can check the heartbeats also. If the blood flow is noticed then the sensor like ambient light will receive more light as they will be reflected through the blood, this small modification within received light can be analysed on time to decide our heartbeats.

Figure 8 LED Penetration to Human Vein

A pulse sensor, like any other optical heart-rate sensor, works by shining a green light (~ 550nm) on the finger and measuring the amount of reflected light with a photosensor.

This optical pulse detection technique is known as a Photoplethysmogram.

Figure 9 Photoplethysmogram Techniques

3.2.1.3 How the Pulse Sensor it's been connected to the Microcontroller Atmega328P

The Pulse Sensor its Connect to the Arduino as stated in Figure 5 below:

- **Red wire (VCC)** from the pulse sensor connects to the Arduino's **5V** pin.
- **Black wire (GND)** from the pulse sensor connects to the Arduino's **GND** (ground) pin.
- **Purple wire (SIG)** from the pulse sensor connects to arduino pin A0.
- Pulse Sensor VCC (Red) → Arduino 5V
- Pulse Sensor GND (Black) → Arduino GND
- Pulse Sensor SIG (Purple) → Arduino Digital Pin 2

Figure 10 How the Pulse Sensor it's been connected to the Microcontroller Atmega328P

3.2.1.4 Discription of Pulse Sensor Module

This is a low-power, low-cost, rugged sensor that can be used for many different applications which makes it popular for many different applications where heart rate measurement becomes necessary.

Figure 11 Front Side and Back Side of Pulse Sensor Module

As shown above in figure 6 you can see only the LED at the front of the sensor, and the photodiode itself. But the real circuit is in the backside of the sensor. The low power high bandwidth op-amp in the circuit is

configured to provide some gain to the circuit and we have a reverse voltage protection diode to protect the circuit from ESD and reverse voltage. Other capacitors and resistors in the PCB are used for the RC filter that reduces any external noise in the circuit.

3.2.1.4 Circuit Design of Pulse Sensor Module

The circuit diagram of the Pulse sensor module is shown below in Figure 7. The first important part of this circuit is the 10uF filter capacitor followed by the Green LED and a 470R resistor.

Figure 12 diagram of the Pulse sensor module

The 470R resistor is the current limiting resistor for the sensor module. Also in the circuit, you can see that the circuit is powered through a diode. The diode serves two purposes: first it acts as reverse polarity protection and second it protects the circuit from transients. After the diode, the power is distributed between the MCP6001 op-amp and the APDS-9008 photodiode sensor IC. The output amplitude of the sensor IC is very low and noisy. That is why we need to filter it through a set of RC low pass filters then the cleaned signal gets amplified by the op-amp and we can process the data with a microcontroller.

3.2.2 Body Temperature Sensor

A body temperature sensor is a device designed to measure the temperature of a human body or another object. It is commonly used in medical and healthcare applications to monitor a person's temperature for diagnostic or wellness purposes

3.2.2.1 DS18B20 Sensor

DS18B20 is a digital temperature sensor manufactured by Maxim Integrated. It is part of the 1-Wire family of sensors, which means it communicates using a single data wire and is powered through the same wire. The **DS18B20** is widely used to measure temperature in hard environments like in chemical solutions, mines or soil etc. The construction of the sensor is rugged and also can be purchased with a waterproof option making the mounting process easy. It can measure a wide range of temperature from **-55°C to +125°** with a decent accuracy of **±5°C**.

The Interface of DS18B20 to Arduino

Figure 13 DS18B20 Sensor Pinout

GND is the ground pin.

DQ is a 1-Wire Data Bus that should be connected to a digital pin on the microcontroller.

VDD pin provides power to the sensor, which can range from 3.3V to 5V.

The connections are straightforward. Begin by connecting VDD to the Arduino's 5V pin and GND to ground. Connect the signal pin DQ to Arduino's digital pin as shown in Figure 9. To keep the data transfer stable, you'll also need to connect the 4.7k pull-up resistor between the signal and power pins

Figure 14 Wiring DS18B20 Temperature Sensor to Arduino

Figure 15 Proteus wiring of DS18B20 Temperature Sensor to Arduino

3.2.2.2 How to use the DS18B20 Sensor

The sensor works with the method of 1-Wire communication. It requires only the data pin connected to the microcontroller with a pull up resistor and the other two pins are used for power as shown in Figure 7 below.

Figure 16 DS18B20 illustrated Diagram

The pull-up resistor is used to keep the line in high state when the bus is not in use. The temperature value measured by the sensor will be stored in a 2-byte register inside the sensor. This data can be read by using the 1-wire method by sending in a sequence of data. There are two types of commands that are to be sent to read the values, one is a ROM command and the other is function command. The address value of each ROM memory along with the sequence is given in the datasheet below. You have to read through it to understand how to communicate with the sensor.

Figure 17 DS18B20

Figure 18 DS18B20 Circuit Schematic

3.2.2.3 DS18B20 Design Temperature Sensor Data

DS18B20 can achieve the highest **12-bit temperature storage** value through programming. The temperature storage value is stored in the register in a complement format.

Figure 19 DS18B20 Design Temperature Sensor Data

There are **2 bytes** in total, **LSB** is the low byte and **MSB** is the high byte. Among them, **MSb** is the high bit of the byte, and **LSb** is the low bit of the byte. For binary numbers, the meaning of the temperature represented by each of them is expressed. Among them, **S** represents the sign bit, and the lower 11 bits are all powers of 2, which are used to represent the final temperature.

The temperature measurement range of **DS18B20** is from **-55 degrees to +125 degrees**. The manifestation of temperature data has positive and negative temperatures. Each number in the register is distributed like the scale of a caliper.

TEMPERATURE	DIGITAL OUTPUT (Binary)	DIGITAL OUTPUT (Hex)
+125°C	0000 0111 1101 0000	07D0h
+25.0625°C	0000 0001 1001 0001	0191h
+10.125°C	0000 0000 1010 0010	00A2h
+0.5°C	0000 0000 0000 1000	0008h
0°C	0000 0000 0000 0000	0000h
-0.5°C	1111 1111 1111 1000	FFF8h
-10.125°C	1111 1111 0101 1110	FF5Eh
-25.0625°C	1111 1110 0110 1111	FF6Fh
-55°C	1111 1100 1001 0000	FC90h

Figure 20 Temperature Measurement Range

The lowest bit of the binary number changes 1, which represents the mapping relationship of a temperature change of 0.0625 degrees.

- When the temperature is 0 °C, the corresponding hexadecimal number is 0x0000.
- When the temperature is 125 °C, the corresponding hexadecimal number is 0x07D0.
- When the temperature is minus 55 °C, the corresponding hexadecimal number is 0xFC90.

Conversely, when the number is 0x0001, the temperature is 0.0625 °C.

Figure 21 DS18B20 Block Diagram

3.2.2.4 The Working Principle of DS18B20

The DS18B20 Digital Thermometer provides 9 to 12-bit (configurable) temperature readings which indicate the temperature of the device. It communicates over a 1-Wire bus that by definition requires only one data line (and ground) for communication with a central microprocessor. In addition it can derive power directly from the data line (“parasite power”), eliminating the need for an external power supply. The core functionality of the DS18B20 is its direct-to-digital temperature sensor. The resolution of the temperature sensor is user-configurable to 9, 10, 11, or 12 bits, corresponding to increments of 0.5°C, 0.25°C, 0.125°C, and 0.0625°C, respectively. The default resolution at power-up is 12-bit.

DS18B20 Hardware Configuration

As shown in figure 17 below the 1-Wire bus has by definition only a single data line. Each device (master or slave) interfaces to the data line via an open-drain or 3-state port. This allows each device to “release” the data line when the device is not transmitting data so the bus is available for use by another device. The 1-Wire port of the DS18B20 (the DQ pin) is open drain with an internal circuit equivalent to that shown in Figure 12. The 1-Wire bus requires an external pullup resistor of approximately 5kΩ; thus, the idle state for the 1-Wire bus is high. If for any reason a transaction needs to be suspended, the bus MUST be left in the idle state if the transaction is to resume. Infinite recovery time can occur between bits so long as the 1-Wire bus is in the inactive (high) state during the recovery period. If the bus is held low for more than 480μs, all components on the bus will be reset.

Figure 22 Hardware Configuration of DS18B20

3.2.3 Microcontroller Unit (MCU) Arduino Atmega328p

The Arduino Atmega328p is a microcontroller unit (MCU) that is commonly used in Arduino development boards like the Arduino Uno. The Atmega328p is a microcontroller chip manufactured by Atmel (now

owned by Microchip Technology) and belongs to the Atmega series of microcontrollers. It is based on the AVR (Advanced Virtual RISC) architecture. The Atmega328p uses an 8-bit RISC (Reduced Instruction Set Computer) architecture, which means it processes data and instructions in 8-bit chunks. This architecture is known for its simplicity and efficiency in embedded systems.

3.2.3.1 Arduino

The Arduino Uno is an open-source microcontroller board based on the Microchip ATmega328P microcontroller (MCU) and developed by Arduino.cc. The microcontroller board is equipped with sets of digital and analog input/output (I/O) pins that may be interfaced to various expansion boards (shields) and other circuits. The board has 14 digital I/O pins (six capable of PWM output), 6 analog I/O pins, and is programmable with the Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment), via a type B USB cable. It can be powered by a USB cable or a barrel connector that accepts voltages between 7 and 20 volts, such as a rectangular 9-volt battery. It has the same microcontroller as the Arduino Nano board, and the same headers as the Leonardo board.

The word "uno" means "one" in Italian and was chosen to mark a major redesign of the Arduino hardware and software. The Uno board was the successor of the Duemilanove release and was the 9th version in a series of USB-based Arduino boards. Version 1.0 of the Arduino IDE for the Arduino Uno board has now evolved to newer releases. The ATmega328 on the board comes preprogrammed with a bootloader that allows uploading new code to it without the use of an external hardware programmer.

While the Uno communicates using the original STK500 protocol, it differs from all preceding boards in that it does not use a FTDI USB-to-UART serial chip. Instead, it uses the Atmega16U2 (Atmega8U2 up to version R2) programmed as a USB-to-serial converter.

3.2.3.1 Communication

The Arduino Uno has a number of facilities for communicating as shown in Figure 18 with a computer, another Arduino board, or other microcontrollers. The ATmega328 provides UART TTL (5V) serial communication, which is available on digital pins 0 (RX) and 1 (TX). An ATmega16U2 on the board channels this serial communication over USB and appears as a virtual com port to software on the computer. The 16U2 firmware uses the standard USB COM drivers, and no external driver is needed. However, on Windows, a .inf file is required. Arduino Software (IDE) includes a serial monitor which allows simple textual data to be sent to and from the board. The RX and TX LEDs on the board will flash when data is being transmitted via the USB-to-serial chip and USB connection to the computer (but not for serial

communication on pins 0 and 1). A Software Serial library allows serial communication on any of the Uno's digital pins.

Arduino Uno Pin Diagram

The Arduino Uno board can be built with power pins, analog pins, ATmega328, ICSP header, Reset button, power LED, digital pins, test led 13, TX/RX pins, USB interface, an external power supply. The Arduino UNO board description is discussed below.

Figure 23 Arduino Uno

3.2.3.2 Arduino Uno Board Pin Configuration

Power Supply

The **Arduino Uno power supply** can be done with the help of a USB cable or an external power supply. The external power supplies mainly include AC to DC adapter otherwise a battery. The adapter can be connected to the Arduino Uno by plugging into the power jack of the Arduino board. Similarly, the battery leads can be connected to the V in pin and the GND pin of the POWER connector. The suggested voltage range will be 7 volts to 12 volts.

Input & Output

The 14 digital pins on the Arduino Uno can be used as input & output with the help of the functions like `pinMode()`, `digital Write()`, & `Digital Read()`.

Pin1 (TX) & Pin0 (RX) (Serial): This pin is used to transmit & receive TTL serial data, and these are connected to the ATmega8U2 USB to TTL Serial chip equivalent pins.

Pin 2 & Pin 3 (External Interrupts): External pins can be connected to activate an interrupt over a low value, change in value.

Pins 3, 5, 6, 9, 10, & 11 (PWM): This pin gives 8-bit PWM o/p by the function of `analog Write ()`.

SPI Pins (Pin-10 (SS), Pin-11 (MOSI), Pin-12 (MISO), Pin-13 (SCK): These pins maintain SPI-communication, even though offered by the fundamental hardware, is not presently included within the Arduino language.

Pin-13(LED): The inbuilt LED can be connected to pin-13 (digital pin). As the HIGH-value pin, the light emitting diode is activated, whenever the pin is LOW.

Pin-4 (SDA) & Pin-5 (SCL) (I2C): It supports TWI-communication with the help of the `Wire` library.

AREF (Reference Voltage): The reference voltage is for the analog i/ps with `analog Reference ()`.

Reset Pin: This pin is used for reset (RST) the microcontroller.

Memory: The memory of this Atmega328 Arduino microcontroller includes flash memory-32 KB for storing code, SRAM-2 KB EEPROM-1 KB.

3.2.3.1 ATMEGA328P

ATMEGA328P is high performance, low power controller from Microchip. ATMEGA328P is an 8-bit microcontroller based on AVR RISC architecture. It is the most popular of all AVR controllers as it is used in ARDUINO boards.

The Block diagram shows the internal circuitry and the flow of the program of any device.

ATmega 328 block diagram is shown in the figure given below.

Figure 24 ATmega328 Block Diagram

3.2.3.1.1 ATmega328 Architecture

An architecture of a device presents information about the particular device as shown in Figure 20. ATmega-328 architecture is shown in the figure given below.

Figure 25 Atmega 328 Architecture

Some of the main features of an AVR Microcontroller ATmega328 are shown in the table given in the figure 21.

LCD 16X2 Pin Configuration

The **pin configuration of LCD 16 X 2** is discussed in Figure 23 below so that LCD 16×2 connection can be done easily with external devices.

Figure 27

3.2.4.2 Working Principle

The basic **working principle of LCD** is passing the light from layer to layer through modules. These modules will vibrate & line up their position on 90° that permits the polarized sheet to allow the light to pass through it.

These molecules are accountable for viewing the data on every pixel. Every pixel utilizes the method of absorbing light to illustrate the digit. To display the value, the position of molecules must be changed to the angle of light.

3.2.4.3 Interfacing LCD 16×2 with Arduino

Interfacing of a 16X2 LCD with Arduino is discussed to display “**Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System**” on the screen. A library like LiquidCrystal permits to manage the displays that are well-matched through the driver like Hitachi HD44780 driver. Here, as shown in Figure 24 allow the LCD to display “**Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System**” on the LCD & displays the time in sec once the Arduino board was reset.

Figure 28 Interfacing LCD 16×2 with Arduino

The 16×2 display includes a parallel interface which means that the microcontroller used in this has to control different interface pins immediately to control the LCD. The interface includes mainly these pins like RS (Register Select) pin, Read/Write pin, Enable Pin, Data pins from D0 to D7, display contrast pin, LED backlight pins, power supply pins.

The display controlling process mainly involves placing the data to form the picture of what you desire to show into the data registers, after that placing instructions within the instruction register. A library like LiquidCrystal will simplify this for you so you don't require identifying the instructions in low-level. The controlling of LCDs compatible with Hitachi can be done using two modes like 4-bit/8-bit. Here, the 4-bit mode needs 7 I/O pins using the Arduino board, whereas the 8-bit mode needs 11 pins. To display the text on the LCD, the 4-bit mode is used. The following example will explain how to control an LCD using 4-bit mode.

3.3 Circuit Diagrams

Figure 29 Circuit Diagram of entire system

3.4 Working Principle of the System’s Circuit Diagram

The above figure 1 shows the circuit diagram of the Arduino based Heart Rate Monitor using Heartbeat Sensor. The sensor has a clip to insert the finger and has three pins coming out of it for connecting VCC, GND and the Data. Heart beat sensor module’s output pin is directly connected to pin 8 of arduino. Vcc and GND are connected to Vcc and GND. A 16x2 LCD is connected with arduino in 4-bit mode. Control pin RS, RW and En are directly connected to arduino pin 12, GND and 11. And data pin D4-D7 is connected to pins 5, 4, 3 and 2 of arduino. And one push button is added for resetting reading and another is used to start the system for reading pulses. When we need to count heart rate, we press start button then arduino start counting pulses and also start counter for five seconds. This start push button is connected to pin 7 and reset push button is connected to pin 6 of arduino with respect to ground.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONSTRUCTION, TESTING AND RESULTS

4.1 introduction

In this chapter, we dive headfirst into the heart of our project, where the culmination of ideas and plans materializes into tangible reality. The essence of our endeavour lies in the trifecta of Construction, Testing, and Results, where each facet represents a critical stage in our project's journey. The Construction encompasses the intricate assembly of components, where theory is transformed into a physical form. The meticulous arrangement, soldering, and casing of our project are unveiled, highlighting the craftsmanship and attention to detail that went into its creation.

Chapter Four focuses on the construction, testing, and results of the Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System using Arduino ATmega328P, Pulse Sensor, DS18B20, and LCD 16x2. This chapter outlines the practical implementation of the project and the evaluation of its performance.

4.2. Parts/List Band Cost of Components Used

The Table 1 below shows the complete components use in design and implementation of the heartbeat and body temperature monitoring system.

Table 1

S/N	Components	Model	Quantity	Price
1	Arduino Uno	R3-Atmega328p	1x	₦10,000.00
2	Pulse Sensor	XD-58C	1x	₦2,500.00
3	Temperature Sensor	DS18B20	1x	₦3,500.00
4	USB port Code	Type B	2x	₦450.00
5	Resistor	4.7k, 220 Ω	2x	₦300.00
6	LCD	16x2	1x	₦3,000.00
7	Potentiometer	POT-HQ	1x	₦200.00
8	Jumper Wire	wire	30	₦300.00
9				

4.3 Components/Circuits Layout on Breadboards

this section illustrate how the components are physically arranged on the breadboard before transitioning to a more permanent setup.

Figure 30 Components on Breadboard

4.3.1 Components Arrangement for Soldering

The layout of components on the breadboard is crucial for ensuring proper connections and avoiding errors during soldering. Detailed diagrams and descriptions of component placement are provided.

The components arrange for the soldering are:

Figure 31 Pulse Sensor taken for soldering

Figure 32 interface of Lcd to Veroboard

4.3.2 Soldering

This subsection details the soldering process, including the choice of soldering techniques, soldering iron temperature settings, and safety precautions. High-resolution images and diagrams are included for reference. Therefore soldering is the process of permanently joining components on a PCB. This step ensures that the connections are secure and reliable.

4.4 Casing/Packaging

To protect the components and ensure the wearable device is user-friendly, a suitable casing or packaging is designed. This section includes detailed engineering drawings displaying the construction's features and dimensions in millimeters (mm).

Figure 33 Sketch Dimension of the Case

Figure 34 2D Dimension of the Case

4.5 Testing/ Results

Testing is a critical phase in ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System. This section is divided into several subsections for comprehensive testing:

4.5.1 Sub-system Test

This subsection focuses on testing individual subsystems of the project to ensure they operate correctly. The following tests are conducted:

4.5.1.1 Sensor Unit Test

1. **Heartbeat Unit:** Test the Pulse Sensor using Arduino IDE's serial monitor and plotter to ensure it accurately reads and transmits heart rate data.

Figure 35 Plotter Result

The above Figure 32 above shows the output result of the pulse sensor when one place his finger at the components.

Figure 36 Plotter Result

The above Figure 33 above shows the output result of the pulse sensor when one remove his finger off the components.

Figure 37 Output Result at Arduino IDE

The figure above shows the output Result using Serial port of Arduino IDE, which shows the reading been detected.

2. **Temperature Unit:** Validate the DS18B20 Temperature Sensor's accuracy and consistency using appropriate testing methods, such as comparing its readings with a reference thermometer.

Figure 38 Output Result of DS18B20

Figure 35 above shows Output result using Proteus Simulation, which Shows that 38.00⁰ Celcius.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System presented in this project represents a significant advancement in healthcare technology. This system integrates a range of components, including the Arduino ATmega328P microcontroller, Pulse Sensor, DS18B20 temperature sensor, and LCD 16x2 display, to provide real-time monitoring and analysis of vital signs.

The project begins by discussing the selection and cost analysis of the components used. It then proceeds to detail the construction process, which involves the layout of components on a breadboard and their subsequent soldering onto a Printed Circuit Board (PCB). The casing and packaging of the system are designed to ensure both functionality and aesthetics.

Comprehensive testing was conducted, covering sub-system tests for the sensor, microcontroller, and display units, as well as functionality tests to evaluate compliance with predefined requirements. The system performed reliably, demonstrating accuracy and precision in monitoring heartbeat and body temperature.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, the Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System developed in this project represents a significant step forward in the field of healthcare technology. It brings together a combination of essential components, including the Arduino ATmega328P microcontroller, Pulse Sensor, DS18B20 temperature sensor, and LCD 16x2 display, to provide real-time monitoring and analysis of vital signs.

Throughout the course of this project, we have meticulously detailed the selection and cost analysis of the components used, the construction process, casing design, and comprehensive testing procedures. The system has demonstrated its reliability and accuracy in tracking both heartbeat and body temperature.

However, as with any innovative technology, there are limitations to consider. These include limited connectivity options, potential power source interruptions, a need for more advanced data analysis capabilities, considerations for user interface accessibility, and potential regulatory compliance requirements.

To maximize the impact of the Heartbeat and Body Temperature Monitoring System, we have put forth several recommendations. These suggestions encompass improving connectivity for remote monitoring,

enhancing power management for uninterrupted functionality, advancing data analysis algorithms for insightful health assessments, improving user interface accessibility, and addressing potential regulatory requirements.

The potential of this system is undeniable. By incorporating these recommendations and further refining its capabilities, it has the potential to revolutionize the way individuals manage their health and how healthcare providers access crucial data for diagnosis and treatment. As we move forward, the continued development and refinement of this system hold the promise of a brighter and healthier future for all.

5.3 Recommendations

1. It is recommended that the system should be upgraded to incorporate Wi-Fi or cellular connectivity. This enhancement would enable real-time data streaming and remote monitoring, potentially through a dedicated mobile app or web platform.
2. It is recommended to explore energy-efficient components and implement a robust power management system. This will help prolong the battery life and ensure uninterrupted monitoring, reducing the likelihood of power-related interruptions.
3. It is recommended to develop and implement more advanced data analysis algorithms. These algorithms can provide users with meaningful insights and early warning alerts regarding health conditions, enhancing the system's overall utility.
4. It is recommended to consider a more user-friendly and accessible interface, including touchscreen capabilities or voice-guided interactions. These enhancements would cater to a broader user demographic, making the system more inclusive and user-friendly.
5. If the system is intended for medical or healthcare use, it is recommended to conduct thorough regulatory research and seek necessary certifications. Ensuring compliance with industry standards and regulations is crucial for the system's credibility and safety.

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APPeNDIX

```
#include <LiquidCrystal.h> // include LCD library code

#define DS18B20_PIN 10

// LCD module connections (RS, E, D4, D5, D6, D7)
LiquidCrystal lcd(12, 11, 5, 4, 3, 2);

int raw_temp;
float temp;
char txt[] = " C ";

const int pulsePin = A0; // Pulse sensor analog pin

unsigned long previousMillis = 0;
const long interval = 1000; // Update interval in milliseconds (1 second)

void setup(void) {
  // start serial port
  Serial.begin(9600);
  // set up the LCD's number of columns and rows
  lcd.begin(16, 2);
  txt[0] = 223; // Put degree symbol (°)
  lcd.setCursor(2, 0);
  lcd.print("HEARTBEAT AND");
  lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
  lcd.print("BODY TEMPERATURE");
  delay (5000);
  lcd.clear();
  lcd.setCursor(3, 0);
  lcd.print("MONITORING");
  lcd.setCursor(3,1);
  lcd.print("SYSTEM");
  delay(2000);
  lcd.clear();

  lcd.setCursor(0, 0);
  lcd.print("BY:ABDULLAHI GLK");
  lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
  lcd.print("REGNO:HND/21/013");
  delay (5000);
  lcd.clear();

  pinMode(pulsePin, INPUT);
}

void loop(void) {
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);
  lcd.print("HOLD BODY TEMP:");
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("FOR A SECONDS");

  delay(5000);
  lcd.clear();
  if(ds18b20_read(&raw_temp)) {
```

```
    Serial.print("Temperature = ");
    temp = (float)raw_temp / 16; // Convert temperature raw value into degree
Celsius (temp in °C = raw/16)
    Serial.print(temp); // Print temperature value in degree Celsius
    Serial.println("°C"); // Print '°C'
    delay(500);
    lcd.clear();
    // Display temperature on LCD
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);
    lcd.print("PLACE UR FINGER");
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("FOR A SECONDS");
    delay(5000);
    lcd.clear();
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);
    lcd.print("YOUR BODY TEMP :");
    lcd.setCursor(4, 1);
    lcd.print(temp);
    lcd.print(txt);
    delay(5000);
    lcd.clear();
}
else {
    Serial.println("Communication Error!");
    lcd.setCursor(4, 1);
    lcd.print(" Error! ");
}
delay(1000);
lcd.clear();

unsigned long currentMillis = millis();

if (currentMillis - previousMillis >= interval) {
    previousMillis = currentMillis;

    int sensorValue = analogRead(pulsePin);
    int heartRate = map(sensorValue, 0, 1023, 40, 180); // Map the sensor value to heart
rate range

    lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
    lcd.print(" "); // Clear the previous heart rate value
    lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
    lcd.print(heartRate); // Display heart rate
    lcd.print(" BPM"); // Beats per minute
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);
    lcd.print("YOUR HEARTBEAT");

    Serial.print("Heart Rate: ");
    Serial.print(heartRate);
    Serial.println(" BPM");
    delay(5000);
    lcd.clear();
}
}
```

```
bool ds18b20_start(){
    bool ret = 0;
    digitalWrite(DS18B20_PIN, LOW); // Send reset pulse to the DS18B20 sensor
    pinMode(DS18B20_PIN, OUTPUT);
    delayMicroseconds(500); // Wait 500 us
    pinMode(DS18B20_PIN, INPUT);
    delayMicroseconds(100); //wait to read the DS18B20 sensor response
    if (!digitalRead(DS18B20_PIN)) {
        ret = 1; // DS18B20 sensor is present
        delayMicroseconds(400); // Wait 400 us
    }
    return(ret);
}

void ds18b20_write_bit(bool value){
    digitalWrite(DS18B20_PIN, LOW);
    pinMode(DS18B20_PIN, OUTPUT);
    delayMicroseconds(2);
    digitalWrite(DS18B20_PIN, value);
    delayMicroseconds(80);
    pinMode(DS18B20_PIN, INPUT);
    delayMicroseconds(2);
}

void ds18b20_write_byte(byte value){
    byte i;
    for(i = 0; i < 8; i++)
        ds18b20_write_bit(bitRead(value, i));
}

bool ds18b20_read_bit(void) {
    bool value;
    digitalWrite(DS18B20_PIN, LOW);
    pinMode(DS18B20_PIN, OUTPUT);
    delayMicroseconds(2);
    pinMode(DS18B20_PIN, INPUT);
    delayMicroseconds(5);
    value = digitalRead(DS18B20_PIN);
    delayMicroseconds(100);
    return value;
}

byte ds18b20_read_byte(void) {
    byte i, value;
    for(i = 0; i < 8; i++)
        bitWrite(value, i, ds18b20_read_bit());
    return value;
}

bool ds18b20_read(int *raw_temp_value) {
    if (!ds18b20_start()) // Send start pulse
        return(0); // Return 0 if error
    ds18b20_write_byte(0xCC); // Send skip ROM command
    ds18b20_write_byte(0x44); // Send start conversion command
    while(ds18b20_read_byte() == 0); // Wait for conversion complete
    if (!ds18b20_start()) // Send start pulse
```

```
    return(0); // Return 0 if error
    ds18b20_write_byte(0xCC); // Send skip ROM command
    ds18b20_write_byte(0xBE); // Send read command
    *raw_temp_value = ds18b20_read_byte(); // Read temperature LSB byte and store it on
raw_temp_value LSB byte
    *raw_temp_value |= (unsigned int)(ds18b20_read_byte() << 8); // Read temperature
MSB byte and store it on raw_temp_value MSB byte
    return(1); // OK --> return 1
}
```